

THE PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF MULTI - FREQUENCY HIGH BANDWIDTH PATCH ANTENNA

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ABSTRACT

The cellular industry came into existence about 30 years ago and as of today, there are approximately 150 million subscribers worldwide. The cellular industry generates \$30 billion in annual revenues and is one of the fastest growing industries. The cellular handsets being used in the 1980s were bulky and heavy. Advancements in VLSI technology have enabled size reduction for the various microprocessors and signal processing chips being used in cellular phones. Another method for reducing handset size is by using more compact antennas. The aim of this thesis is to design such a compact antenna for use in wireless/cellular devices. A Microstrip Patch Antenna consists of a dielectric substrate on one side of a patch, with a ground plane on the other side. Due to its advantages such as low weight and volume, low profile planar configuration, low fabrication costs and capability to integrate with microwave integrated circuits (MICs), the microstrip patch antenna is very well suited for applications such as cellular phones, pagers, missile systems, and satellite communications systems. A compact, multiband microstrip patch antenna is designed for use in a cellular phone at 1.8 GHz, 2.5GHz, and 6.3GHz. The results obtained provide a workable antenna design for incorporation in a cellular phone.

Key words: VLSI, MICs, Microstrip Patch Antenna, wireless/cellular devices

INTRODUCTION

In 1897, Guglielmo Marconi demonstrated radio's ability to provide continuous contact with ships sailing across the English Channel. Since then, numerous advances have been made in the field of wireless communications. Numerous experiments were carried out by different researchers to make use of electromagnetic waves to carry information.

Antennas are metallic structures designed for radiating and receiving electromagnetic energy. An antenna acts as a transitional structure between the guiding device (e.g. waveguide, transmission line) and the free space. The official IEEE definition of an antenna as given by Stutzman and Thiele follows the concept: "That part of a transmitting or receiving system that is designed to radiate or receive electromagnetic waves". Antennas come in different shapes and sizes to suit different types of wireless applications. The characteristics of an antenna are very much determined by its shape, size and the type of

material that it is made of. In its most basic form, a Microstrip patch antenna consists of a radiating patch on one side of a dielectric substrate which has a ground plane on the other side. The patch is generally made of conducting material such as copper or gold and can take any possible shape. The radiating patch and the feed lines are usually photo etched on the dielectric substrate.

Methods of Analysis

The most popular models for the analysis of Microstrip patch antennas are the transmission line model, cavity model, and full wave model [5] (which include primarily integral equations/Moment Method). The transmission line model is the simplest of all and it gives good physical insight but it is less accurate. The cavity model is more accurate and gives good physical insight but is complex in nature. The full wave models are extremely accurate, versatile and can treat single elements, finite and infinite arrays, stacked elements, arbitrary shaped elements and coupling. These give less insight as compared to the two models mentioned above and are far more complex in nature.

HFSS

in the process of setting up and running a simulation in HFSS. The version used is Agilent version 5.6. HFSS is a software package for electromagnetic modeling and analysis of passive, three-dimensional structures. It helps the user to observe and analyze various electromagnetic properties of the structure such as radiation patterns and scattering parameters. While it is not necessary to be an expert in numerical electromagnetic to use HFSS, it is important to understand each step of the modeling process in details so as to obtain accurate and reliable results. This chapter aims to provide this understanding from a general point of view.

Microstrip Patch Antenna : Design And Results

A compact rectangular microstrip patch antenna is designed for use in cellular phones. Finally, the results obtained from the simulations that are done using HFSS are demonstrated.

a) Design Specifications

The three essential parameters for the design of a rectangular Microstrip Patch Antenna are:

- **Frequency of operation (f_o):** The resonant frequency of the antenna must be selected appropriately. The GSM, UMTS, WLAN uses the frequency range from 1.8, 2.5, 6.3GHz. Hence the antenna designed must be able to operate in this frequency range. The resonant frequency selected for my design is 1.8, 2.5, 6.3GHz.
- **Dielectric constant of the substrate (ϵ_r):** The dielectric material selected for my design is Fr4epoxy which has a dielectric constant of 4.4. A substrate with a high dielectric constant has been selected since it reduces the dimensions of the antenna.

• **Height of dielectric substrate (h):** For the microstrip patch antenna to be used in cellular phones, it is essential that the antenna is not bulky. Hence, the height of the dielectric substrate is selected as 1.6 mm.

Hence, the essential parameters for the design are:

$$f_o = 1.8, 2.5, 6.3 \text{ GHz}$$

$$\epsilon_r = 4.4$$

$$h = 1.6 \text{ mm}$$

b) Design Procedure:

As we have designed four rectangular patch antennas with different slot configurations i.e. inverted f slot, inverted l slot, parallel vertical slot, and parallel f slots. First of all basic antenna geometry is discussed and then one by one all the antennas with different slot configurations are discussed with their simulation results. In the end all are compared and the best one is chosen that is inverted l.

Basic Antenna Geometry:

As shown below is the basic antenna geometry here the dimensions are:

Length of the substrate: 50mm

Width of the substrate: 35mm

Length of the patch: 32mm

Width of the patch: 18mm

Length of feed: 13mm

Width of feed: 4.2

Length of partial ground plane: 12.5mm

Figure 1: Basic Antenna Geometry

Parallel F-Slot Antenna:

First of all we will discuss the parallel F- antenna .Its basic figure and dimensions are given below.

Figure 2: Antenna with parallel F slot

As shown above all the geometry is same except the slots are inserted to improve its parameters. After simulating it on HFSS we get the following results. As it can be seen from the figure the antenna is resonating on five frequencies.

Figure 3: S11 Parameters

That are 1.8GHz, 2.5GHz, 5.1GHz, 6.2GHz and 7.2GHz. Thus we see it can be used for GSM/UMTS/WLAN/PCS bands of cellular mobile phones. It is showing -11db dip at 1.8GHz, -14db dip at 2.5GHz, -15db dip at 5.1GHz, -22db dip at 6.2GHz and -18db dip at 7.2GHz. So we see that these are good results for return loss parameters. Its VSWR parameters are also shown below that shows VSWR of 4 at 1.8GHz and 3 at 2.5GHz, 5 at 5.1 GHz, and at 6.2GHz is 3 that is considered to be good.

Figure 4: VSWR Parameters

c) Antenna With Parallel Vertical Slot:

As shown below is the antenna with parallel vertical slots. Basic geometry is same except two parallel vertical slots are added for making antenna more efficient.

Figure 5(A): Parallel Vertical Slot Antenna

As it can be seen that antenna is now resonating at 1.8, 2.5, 6.2 GHz with S11 parameters showing dip at these frequencies of -10db at 1.8, -18 db at 2.5GHz and -32 db at 6.2 GHz. Thus we see antenna that was of five band with parallel f is now of three bands but with better return losses at 2.5 and 6.2 GHz.

Figure 5(B): S11 Parameters

Figure 6 : VSWR Parameters

As can be seen from the parameters VSWR at 1.8 is 1.9 , at 2.5 is 1.2 and at 6.2 is 1.05. These are better VSWR ratings than parallel f slot antenna . Thus we see although resonant frequencies are reduced from five to three but other parameters are coming better. The radiation pattern of this antenna is shown below .As can be seen from the figure it's a directional antenna.

Ansot LLC

Figure 7: Radiation Pattern

d) Antenna With Inverted F- Slot:

Basic geometry of the antenna is shown below. As can be seen only inverted f slots are added.

Figure 8: Inverted F Slot Antenna

As can be seen from the s11 parameters we see antenna is showing resonance at 1.8, 2.5 and 6.2 GHz. But their return loss has improved as compared to other two already explained. As here return loss is -11db,-24db and -22db for the respective frequencies. Similarly for the vswr it is 1.8, 1.2, 1.4 for the respective frequencies. Radiation pattern is almost unidirectional.

Figure 9: S11 Parameters

Figure 10: VSWR Parameters

Figure 11: Radiation Pattern

Antenna With Inverted L -Slot:

Basic geometry of the antenna is shown below. As can be seen only inverted l slots are added.

Figure 12: Inverted L Slot Antenna

As can be seen from the s11 parameters we see antenna is showing resonance at 1.8 ,2.5 and 6.2 GHz. But their return loss has improved as compared to other two already explained. As here return loss is -18db,-22db and -34dbfor the respective frequencies. Similarly for the vswr it is 1.2,1.1,1.09 for the respective frequencies. Radiation pattern is almost unidirectional.

FIGURE 13 : S11 PARAMETERS

FIGURE 14: VSWR Parameters

Figure 15: Radiation Pattern

Comparison and Discussion:

Now we have analyzed all the four antennas we can easily see that if we use the parallel f slot antenna resonating frequencies will increase but the other parameters like return loss, vswr will get decreased. After comparing the results of all the antennas inverted l slot antenna comes out to be best as it has best return losses best vswr and best radiation pattern out of all four antennas .Thus we suggest this antenna for use in mobile phones in GSM/UMTS/WLAN standard.

Conclusions

The aim of this thesis was to design a compact microstrip patch antenna for use in wireless/cellular devices. A typical cellular phone measures about 14.5 cm by 4.5 cm. Hence the antenna designed must be

able to fit in such a cellular phone. As demonstrated by the design and the results obtained in chapter 4, a compact, multiband microstrip patch antenna has been successfully designed. The ground plane dimensions for the patch antenna have been designed to be 12.5 mm by 35 mm and the patch dimensions are 50mm by 18mm. Hence the designed antenna is compact enough to be placed in a typical cellular phone. Radiation pattern plots have been obtained for the desired antenna orientation. The bandwidth obtained for this antenna is 4GHz which should be sufficient for cellular devices. Another area for future work is to extend this concept to a multiband design. It is envisioned in the future, that a single handset would serve a number of applications. When the user would be at home, the handset would operate in the same frequency range as used by cordless phones and thus would be connected to the local telephone exchange. When the user would be outside his house, the handset would connect to the cellular network. On a business trip away from home, the handset would then connect though the satellite network to provide service to the user. These different networks would require that the antenna in the handset is able to operate at separate frequencies. The antenna designed in this thesis is a multiband antenna centered at (1.8, 2.5, 6.2) GHz. Work can be done to design a microstrip patch antenna which can have performance characteristics.

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